

IMPROVING THE CONFLICT RESOLUTION COMPETENCIES OF EDUCATION TEACHERS USING AXEOLOGICAL APPROACHES

Safarbayeva Mokhira

Urgench State Pedagogical Institute

Master's student of theory and history of pedagogy
(by type of activity).

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Annotation: In this article, the methods and methods of effective use of the axeological approach in order to improve the skills of the teachers of educational science in order to eliminate conflicts, and how they should find a solution to the conflicts that arise in the pedagogical process, knowing in advance.

Key words: Axeology, axeological approach, education, training, competence, conflict, pedagogical conflict,

"Education is our future, it is a matter of life and death. Therefore, we have no right to delay reforms in this area. No matter how complicated it is, we must lay the foundations of school education today. Because we We lost time". **Shavkat Mirziyoyev.**

Introduction:

A pedagogue-teacher is a person who has continued since the beginning of the history of human society, and at the same time has always been respected by society and the public. O'tkir Hoshimov in his work "Writings on the border of the notebook" assesses the role of the teacher in society and emphasizes the following points: If a farmer sows a bad seed, he alone reaps the bitter "harvest", "takes", that year if a teacher sows a bad seed in a child's heart, the whole society will reap the bitter "harvest". After twenty years... Those who say that a teacher does not create material wealth are a bomb that explodes the society from the inside!

Processes of training highly qualified pedagogic personnel that meet the requirements of the time are the main requirements of the international labor market today. The reason is that society needs people who think independently, who can express themselves, and who can make an objective assessment of themselves. They are the driving forces of the development of society. This, in turn, creates the need to update the content of continuous education that serves to develop the professional competence of specialists and to widely introduce advanced foreign experiences into practice. One of the professional competencies that teachers of education should have is the ability to resolve pedagogical conflicts that arise during training and to combine the axeological approach in resolving these conflicts.

Conflict is a form of social interaction between two or more subjects that occurs due to the incompatibility of desires, interests, values or concepts. It is known that there are concepts of "Conflict" and "conflict situation", and the main task for the pedagogue is to distinguish these concepts from each other.

A conflict situation is a mismatch of people's interests that creates a real conflict between social entities. The main sign is the emergence of the subject of the dispute, but the absence of open active struggle. That is, during the development of a conflict, a conflict situation always occurs before the conflict, which is its basis.

Currently, four types of conflicts are shown in pedagogy:

- internal personality, reflecting the struggle of motives, interests, passions, and interests of a person approximately equal in strength;
- interpersonal, represents individuals striving to achieve opposite goals in their life activities;
- it is distinguished by the participation of intergroup, social groups that pursue incompatible goals and hinder each other in the way of their implementation as conflict parties;
- personal-group-occurs when a person's behavior does not correspond to the rules and expectations of the group.

He acknowledged that the issue of pedagogical conflict and its elimination is very urgent in the literature on pedagogy. Pedagogical conflicts are conflicts that may arise between a teacher and a student during the educational process. Pedagogical conflicts, like any kind of conflict, are based on mutual contradictions. Conflicts arise due to the fact that groups do not support each other on certain issues or situations.

Conflicts between teachers and students should be analyzed at three levels:

- ❖ from the point of view of specific objective features of the educational process;
- ❖ from the point of view of the student community of the group, as well as the interpersonal relations between the teacher and the student in certain situations;
- ❖ in terms of age, gender and personal-psychological characteristics of the conflict participants.

The mismatch between the positions of the teacher and the learner causes many conflicts, so it is necessary to know the tried and tested rules used in conflict situations. Awareness of the following rules helps to successfully resolve disputes that arise in the pedagogical process.

Taking control of the conflict situation. This means removing emotional tension. For this, it is necessary to avoid excessive physical exertion and excessive actions. Mimics, poses, gestures not only express a person's inner feelings, but also influence them. Thus, external restraint and calmness!

Influence your partner with your actions. A careful study of the participant's face helps in this, concentrates thoughts and makes it possible to determine his condition. Being able to understand the motives of the interlocutor's actions. The use of mental analysis reduces emotional heat. It is better to express that you understand the complexity of the situation, to explain your situation.

Alignment of purpose. Quickly understand what unites you with the learner and show it. It's about demonstrating that you believe there is a workable solution.

In addition to the above, let's consider conflict resolution tools by combining axiological approaches in the development of pedagogical conflict resolution competencies of education teachers. First, Axiology is the branch of philosophy that studies values and roles and human experience. Axiological approaches provide a framework for analyzing and understanding a variety of fields, including education and conflict analysis.

An axiological approach to improving the conflictual competence of future education teachers includes focusing on values and principles, as well as developing a conscious approach to conflict resolution. Here are some steps to improve conflict situations for future education teachers:

1) Understanding values in conflictology:

- ❖ conduct lessons and discussions about values related to effective conflict resolution.
- ❖ focus on the importance of justice, respect and cooperation in conflict resolution.
- 2) Teaching ethics and professional responsibility:**
- ❖ joining the program of teaching courses on ethics and professional responsibility in the context of conflict resolution.
- ❖ explain to students how ethical principles can be used in conflict resolution.
- 3) Developing empathy and understanding:**
- ❖ conducting lessons on developing empathy and active listening skills.
- ❖ practical exercises aimed at improving teachers' ability to understand other people's points of view and feelings.
- 4) Application of role-playing games and stages of work:**
- ❖ organization of role-playing games where future teachers can experience various conflict scenarios.
- ❖ Analyze cases of real situations in the educational environment to develop conflict resolution strategies and approaches.
- 5) Teaching effective communication skills:**
- ❖ training in effective communication skills, including the ability to express your thoughts clearly and respectfully.
- ❖ develop the ability to ask open questions and maintain dialogue with students, parents and colleagues.
- 6) The practice of conflict resolution in the educational environment:**
- ❖ Creating scenarios and real situations faced by teachers at school, teaching and developing conflict resolution skills.
- ❖ perform practical exercises such as role-playing and modeling conflict situations.
- 7) Use of reflection:**
- ❖ Contribute to future teachers' regular reflection on their experiences in conflict resolution.
- ❖ apply reflective practices to analyze successful and unsuccessful cases of conflict resolution.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, it should be said that by combining conflict resolution competencies in Pedagogy with axiological approaches, future education teachers can develop a solid foundation of values that will guide their ethical decision-making and conflict resolution skills during their pedagogical activities. Also, the axiological approach allows to connect the process of conflict resolution with values, which helps to have a more conscious and effective approach to conflict management in the educational environment.

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